

Effect of urea on the N₂-fixing algal flora in lowland rice at ripening stage

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An inhibitory effect of nitrogen fertilizers, especially urea, on N₂-fixing algal flora in lowland rice fields has frequently been observed during the first stages of rice growth. Because increasing rice canopy reduces the amount of light reaching the floodwater, light often limits algal growth at the end of the rice cycle, especially in rainy season. Information on the late-stage effect of N fertilizers on N₂-fixing algal flora is scarce.

In the azolla demonstration plots at IRRI, rice is transplanted in wide double-row spacing that allows light to reach the water surface throughout the rice cycle. We used the no-N and 100-kg-urea demonstration plots to study the effect of N fertilizer on N₂-fixing blue-green algae (BGA) at grain ripening stage of rice. In the urea plots, N fertilizer was split-applied: ½ before transplanting, ¼ at tillering (14 days after transplanting), and ¼ at panicle initiation.

The algal biomass in the urea plots comprised mainly filamentous green algae (*Spirogyra* sp., *Mougeotia* sp.) in clumps

Colony-forming units of N₂-fixing BGA.^a

Species	Colony-forming units (no.)					
	No nitrogen				100 kg N/ha	
	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻³	10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻³
<i>Nostoc</i>	3	31	322	0	9	69
<i>Anabaena</i>	1	2	4	0	1	0
<i>Calothrix</i>	0	2	23	0	0	0
<i>Fischerella</i>	0	1	7	0	0	0
<i>Oscillatoria</i> ^b	7	—	—	13	198	—
Total	4	36	356	0	10	69
Nb of N ₂ -fixing BGA per cm					7.9 × 10 ⁴	

^a Each value is the mean of 6 counts (triplicate platings of duplicate samples). ^b Nonfixing in aerobiosis - bleached colonies.

10-12 cm in diameter. No-N plots had very large colonies of *Nostoc* sp., 3-8 cm in diameter, and a few small clumps of filamentous green algae.

Composite soil core samples were taken from the plots and the N₂-fixing algal flora was studied by plating suspension-dilutions of soil on Gorham solid medium (1% agar) without N. The medium is selective for N₂-fixing BGA, but permits the growth of some non-N₂-fixing BGA for 2 weeks after inoculation, after which they become discolored but can still be counted. The plates were incubated at 25-30°C under continuous fluorescent light (500lx) for 3 weeks.

Results (see table) showed that urea had a statistically significant inhibiting effect on N₂-fixing BGA. There were five times more colonies in no-N than in urea plots. The N₂-fixing algal flora, dominated by *Nostoc* sp., was more diversified in the no-N plots (4 genera) than in N plots (1 genus). *Oscillatoria*, a non-N₂-fixing BGA, was more abundant in N plots.

Results reported in the literature on the effects of N fertilizers on N₂-fixing microorganisms are controversial, especially those concerning the later stages of rice growth. Our information indicates a clear inhibition of N₂-fixing BGA by urea late in the rice cycle. □

Effect of bushening and nitrogen application on gall midge and rice yield

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Bushening is a shallow-plowing operation with a wooden plow 4-6 wk after broadcast seeding, when there is sufficient water in the field. It loosens, but does not invert soil. The tillage operation improves soil aeration, destroys weeds by incorporating them in the puddle, and redistributes rice seedlings to provide for uniform stand. Bushening is widely used by farmers in Kanki.

We studied the effect of bushening on gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*) incidence at the BAU farm in 1987 kharit. Treatments

Table 1. Effect of bushening and N application on percent silvershoots, Kanke, India.

Treatment	Silvershoot (%)
M1	11 b
M2	16 b
M3	4 a
M4	12 b
SEm (M)	1.78
CD 5%	6.14
N1	8 a
N2	13 b
SEm (N)	1.44
CD 5%	4.68

were no bushening (M1), bushening 30 days after seeding (DS) (M2), bushening 35 DS (M3), and transplanting 30-d-old seedlings (M4). Eighty kg N/ha was applied before bushening (N1) or after

Table 2. Effect of bushening and N application on grain yield. Kanke, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	N1	N2
M1	1.5	1.4
M2	1.5	1.5
M3	1.5	1.2
M4	1.3	1.1
Mean	1.4	1.3
CD 5%	N 0.006	
	M×N 0.027	

(N2). Variety Archana was seeded on 6 Jul.

M3 had the lowest percent silvershoots (Table 1), and N1 nitrogen application gave best results (Table 2). M1 + N1, M2 + N1, and M3 + N1 gave similar yields. □